

**SELECTIVE CATALYST FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF
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ABSTRACT

The work presents the results of research on silver catalysts for the process of selective oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide, obtained by impregnating a ring porous carrier with a solution of the silver amine complex. The influence of magnesium borate and calcium carbonate, introduced in promoting amounts, on the activity, selectivity, and distribution of silver in the porous structure of the carrier was studied. It has been shown that the addition of 0.002-0.0022% magnesium borate contributes to the formation of a stable colloidal solution, a reduction in the size of silver crystallites, and an improvement in their fixation in pores, which increases the active surface area of the metal and the stability of the catalytic layer. Additional administration of 0.001% calcium carbonate has a positive effect on structure formation and increases the selectivity of ethylene oxide formation. Laboratory tests at 20 atm, 220 °C, and a volumetric rate of 4000 h⁻¹ showed that modified catalysts exhibit higher activity and selectivity indicators compared to industrial samples. The optimal silver content was determined - 10-13 wt. %, which ensures the stability of the structure and the long service life of the catalyst.

Currently, catalysts and catalytic processes play a key role in the development of green chemistry, as they allow for more efficient chemical reactions, reducing energy costs and minimizing the formation of by-products. Catalysts accelerate the flow of reactions and provide the possibility of carrying out processes at lower temperatures and pressures, which contributes to the rational use of resources. The modern concept of green chemistry is aimed at developing and implementing new catalytic systems, particularly those based on electrochemical methods that replace toxic reagents and increase atomic efficiency. Obtaining ethylene oxide is one of such promising processes [1].

Ethylene oxide is widely used in the production of non-ionic surfactants, intermediate products of petrochemical synthesis, glycols, alkyl ethers of glycols, ethoxylates of fatty alcohols and alkylphenols, as well as simple polyethers - precursors of polyurethane materials. The dynamic development of these directions necessitates not only increasing the capacity of

units for obtaining ethylene oxide and its further processing products but also improving the operational characteristics of the catalysts used [2-4].

Among the numerous studies in this field, one can note the US patent [5], which describes silver catalytic systems containing promoter amounts of metals - copper, gold, magnesium, zinc, cadmium, mercury, strontium, calcium, niobium, tantalum, molybdenum, tungsten, chromium, vanadium, and preferably barium - in addition to the amount of these elements present in immobilized form on a pre-formed carrier. The compositions of various silver catalysts, mixtures, or binders intended for the synthesis of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide are presented. In particular, silver catalysts containing promotory amounts of at least one element from the lithium, potassium, sodium, rubidium, and cesium groups, as well as a number of promoter metals - copper, gold, magnesium, zinc, cadmium, strontium, calcium, niobium, tantalum, molybdenum, tungsten, chromium, vanadium, and barium - in addition to promotory amounts of alkali metals and alkaline earth elements, preferably barium, have been described.

The US patent [6] provides a description of a silver catalyst modified with an alkaline metal, rhenium, and a component of rare-earth or lanthanide elements.

From the known literature data [7], it follows that the oxidation reaction of ethylene to ethylene oxide occurs on the surface of silver, and silver is the only effective catalyst for this process. In pure silver, the selectivity of the reaction does not exceed 50%, therefore, the introduction of various promoting additives (cesium, rubidium, calcium, potassium, magnesium, barium, etc.) into the catalyst composition is considered the main way to increase selectivity. It is also noted that the use of catalysts in the form of tablets, obtained by introducing promoters into finely dispersed silver powder, leads to excessive silver consumption and complicates the process of loading the catalyst into the reactor.

Currently, catalysts are predominantly used in industry, in which silver oxide is adsorbed by a spherical carrier; at the same time, silver is distributed on the outer surface of the carrier or in the inner pores of spherical granules. Not only the silver oxide content but also the nature of the carrier is of significant importance. Initially, large-pore corundum spheres with a size of 200-400 thousand angstroms were used as carriers. Despite the large volume of pores - 0.26 cm³/g, their specific surface remains extremely small and is about 0.01 m²/g.

To increase the total active surface area of the catalyst, barium sulfate is introduced into the carrier pores. The catalyst is obtained based on silver oxide, lactic acid, silver lactate, and barium sulfate suspension [8].

The carrier impregnation process is carried out with intensive mixing. At a temperature of 160 °C, due to the decomposition of silver lactate, small crystals of metallic silver form on the surface and in the pores of the carrier. In such catalysts, the selectivity of the process is maintained at 62-68%, and the activity is maintained for about two years.

Increasing the active surface area of silver due to a decrease in the pore size of the carrier leads to a difficulty in the placement of barium sulfate crystals in the pore space, causing diffusion inhibition of the reaction and its transition from the kinetic region to the internal diffusion region. As a result, silver accumulation is observed in the central zone of the granules. The silver content in the pores decreases, and due to its migration towards the

center, a significant portion of the metal is not distributed throughout the porous volume of the carrier but is localized primarily on the outer surface.

To increase the active surface area of the catalyst, barium sulfate is introduced into the carrier pores. The catalyst is obtained based on silver oxide, lactic acid, silver lactate, and barium sulfate suspension [8].

The carrier impregnation process is carried out with intensive mixing. At a temperature of 160 °C, silver lactate decomposes on the surface and in the pores of the carrier, forming fine silver crystals. In such catalysts, the selectivity of the process is 62-68%, and the activity is maintained for two years.

Increasing the active surface area of silver due to a decrease in the pore size of the carrier leads to a difficulty in the placement of barium sulfate crystals in the pore space, a diffusion inhibition of the reaction, and its transition from the kinetic region to the internal diffusion region. As a result, silver accumulation is observed in the central part of the granules. The silver content in the pores decreases, and due to its accumulation in the center, a significant portion of the metal is localized primarily on the carrier surface.

Currently, many companies are changing the form of the catalyst and the requirements for the carrier core to eliminate the slowdown of internal diffusion. The geometric shape of the carrier core is represented by rings with a thickness of 2-2.5 mm, and along with large pores that ensure effective contact with silver, small pores must also be present. The carrier in the specified geometry has an outer diameter of 6-6.5 mm, an inner diameter of more than 2 mm, and a height of 5-7 mm.

The material must have a total porosity of about 50-55% and a specific surface area of 0.4-0.5 m²/g. Additionally, it must be resistant to abrasion, crushing, and have sufficient mechanical strength.

Laboratory tests of the catalyst with a starting mixture containing 5% (vol.) ethylene and 5.5% (vol.) oxygen showed that reducing the carrier pore size significantly reduces the selectivity of the process. The test results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Dependence of carrier properties on catalyst selectivity

Carrier properties				Catalyst Properties			Selectivity %
Porosity, %	Bulk density, g/cm ³	Separation strength	Specific surface, m ² /g	Specific surface area of silver	Silver content, % by mass	Silver distribution	
51.	0.77	55.	1.3	0.18	12.9.	In the center	54.4.
54.	71.5	71.5	1.6	0.21	13.1.	Evenly	64.1.

When preparing the catalyst, we used the method of impregnating the carrier with a silver amine complex solution [9]. According to this method, silver nitrate (AgNO₃) reacts with monoethanolamine, initially forming a complex of the composition

[AgH₃NC₂H₄OH]+NO₃, after which the resulting solution is used to impregnate the carrier core.

When a porous carrier core is impregnated with a purified solution of spent aluminum oxide containing silver's amino complex, followed by drying at a temperature of 80-90 °C, fine-crystalline silver particles are formed on its surface. Promoting additives are also adsorbed along with them. To increase the activity and selectivity of the catalyst, it is recommended to use calcium carbonate in the amount of 0.001% of the silver mass as a promoter. The same amount of surfactant - poly (ethylene oxide) is administered. Silver crystals have a size of about 1.5-1.7 thousand tons. Å and are evenly distributed throughout the entire volume of the carrier core porous structure.

During the operation of the catalyst, its activity gradually decreased, which was associated with the aggregation of silver particles. In this regard, research aimed at selecting structure-forming additives has been conducted. As a result, magnesium borate was tested as such an additive, which was introduced in an amount of 0.002% of the mass of silver. The use of a borate-containing additive in the amino-silver complex solution ensures the formation of a stable colloidal solution, contributes to the reduction of the size of silver crystals within the catalyst, and improves their fixation on the carrier surface. This leads to an increase in the active surface area of silver, an increase in catalytic activity, and an increase in the service life of the catalyst.

It has been established that the optimal silver content in the catalyst is 10-13% by mass, which ensures high activity, coating stability, and structural stability.

The experimental results were obtained in laboratory conditions under the following parameters: pressure - 20 atm, ethylene content in the mixture - 5.0%, oxygen - 5.5%, volumetric velocity - 4000 h⁻¹. The obtained data are presented in Figures 1 and 2, where catalysts prepared with the addition of 0.0022% magnesium borate and 0.001% cesium carbonate by weight of silver were investigated. It has been established that the activity and selectivity of catalysts modified with optimal amounts of additives exceed the indicators of previously used industrial samples.

Figure 1. Dependence of the formation of ethylene oxide and CO₂ on the magnesium borate content in the catalyst at a temperature of 220 °C and a volumetric velocity of 4000 h⁻¹.

1 - selectivity; 2 - amount of ethylene oxide; 3 - CO₂ content.

Figure 2. Dependence of the formation of ethylene oxide and CO₂ on the calcium carbonate content in the catalyst with the addition of 0.002% magnesium borate at a volume rate of 4000 h⁻¹ and a temperature of 220 °C.

1 - selectivity; 2 - amount of ethylene oxide; 3 - CO₂ content.

To prepare a silver catalyst with a ring core carrier, aqueous solutions of silver nitrate (AgNO₃), calcium carbonate, magnesium borate, and other functional additives are prepared. In a mixer reactor, a silver amino complex is synthesized based on a silver nitrate solution, modifying additives that affect the structure of the catalyst, and monoethanolamine. The resulting complex is used to impregnate the carrier core in a rotating mixer.

During heat treatment, with a gradual increase in temperature to 90 °C, the amino complex decomposes, causing the pores and surface of the carrier core to be coated with silver's active centers. After this, the temperature is lowered to 30-40 °C. The finished catalyst is washed with distilled water at a temperature of 80-90 °C to remove organic residues of the amino complex, after which impregnation with calcium carbonate is carried out. The obtained catalyst mass is dried at 120 °C, then the catalyst is packaged.

Conclusion. The conducted research confirmed that the structural and chemical parameters of silver catalysts have a decisive influence on the efficiency of the ethylene oxide production process. It has been established that the application of the method of impregnating the carrier with an amine silver complex solution ensures the uniform distribution of the active phase and the formation of fine-crystalline silver particles in the porous structure. The introduction of magnesium borate in an amount of 0.002-0.0022 wt.% contributes to the stabilization of the colloidal silver solution, a decrease in the size of the crystallites, and an improvement in their fixation in the pores, which increases the active surface area of the metal and enhances its catalytic activity. Additional use of calcium carbonate (0.001% by mass.) has a positive effect on structure formation and leads to increased process selectivity.

It has been experimentally confirmed that the optimal silver content in the catalyst is 10-13% by mass, ensuring high activity, coating stability, and a long service life. Modified catalysts exhibit higher selectivity and the formation of ethylene oxide compared to their industrial counterparts, making the proposed approach promising for further implementation in production.

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